

Assessing the Causes and Effects of Truancy on Public Secondary School Students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

Taiwo ALABI

Future Leaders Model College, Ilorin
alabtaiwo82@gmail.com

Kamaldeen Olohundare SUYLYMAN

Department of Educational Foundations,
Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State
sulymanko@fceiwo.edu.ng

Balikis Mosunmola JIMOH

Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling,
Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State
jimohbm@fceiwo.edu.ng

Adenike Florence SIJUADE

Department of Educational Foundations,
Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State
sijuadeaf@fceiwo.edu.ng

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20785913>

Abstract

This study assessed the causes and effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. It adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study was 1,357 in the 42 secondary schools in the area. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 266 teachers out of the 868 in the sampled schools, via the use of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample size determination. Causes and Effects of Truancy on Students Questionnaire (CETSQ) was used for data gathering. The instrument went through validation process and its reliability test through the use Cronbach's Alpha yielded overall reliability index of 0.81. Research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, while t-test was used to test hypotheses. Mean scores less than 2.50 were considered 'Rejected', while 2.50 and above were adjudged 'accepted.' The study found that broken home (Mean = 3.71), poor interest in learning (Mean = 3.05), peer influence (Mean = 3.32), poverty (Mean = 3.40), poor parenting (Mean = 2.99), nonchalant attitudes of teachers (Mean = 3.22), bullying of students (Mean = 3.09), weak school management (Mean = 2.79), societal distractions (Mean = 3.02) and family type (Mean = 3.15) were causes of truancy. The study recommended among other things, that School counsellors should periodically sensitise students on the consequences of truancy, to make them see the reasons they should always be in their classrooms during the school hours to acquire knowledge.

Keywords: Assessing, Causes, Effects, School, Truancy

Introduction

Lesson attendance is very important for students in the process of teaching and learning, at all levels of education. The reason is that for students to acquire adequate knowledge, they have to stay in classrooms and listen to the knowledge being imparted to them by teachers. A student who does not stay in classroom due to one reason or the other, without the knowledge of the school management or teachers, is said to be truant. Sa'ad et al. (2017) viewed truancy as a situation where a student leaves the school without any genuine reason known to the school management or the parents. Adekunle (2015) explained truancy as willingly absenting of oneself from school without permission, leaving with no authorisation and staying away from classrooms while lesson is ongoing. Truancy could also mean a situation whereby a student illegally stays away from classrooms during the school hours, thereby missing knowledge acquisition from teachers. Truancy is one of the bad habits that is rampant among students in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The menace needs to be tackled very well in the interest of the future of Nigerian children.

Sa'ad et al. (2017) observed that a school tends to experience high level truancy when teachers are harsh and bully students, school environment is not conducive, students are bored, management is poor, teachers are not friendly to one students and curriculum irrelevance. The predisposing factors to truancy were identified and found to be student, peer, teacher and school-related. Ehindero (2015) found in his study that the factors responsible for truancy among public secondary school students in Nigeria were school-related, student-related, peer-related and teacher-related. The study conducted by Sa'ad et al. (2017) revealed that the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Azare, Bauchi State were low intelligence or low academic ability, peer influence, poor relationship between teachers and students, nonchalant attitude of school management, the need for students to finance their education, harshness of teachers, non-conducive environment and high level of indiscipline. Van Breda (2014) opined that lack of good guidance, broken homes, drug and alcohol abuse, poverty, domestic problems, poor family support and commitment are some of the contributive factors to the incidence of truant behaviour. Ezeani et al. (2023) argued that attitude of parents towards their children could either motivate or demotivate students' indulgence in truanting behaviour. This means that if parents frown at truancy, it would curb students from making it a regular habit, but if the parents welcome it because it gives them opportunity to derive some benefits from their children while others are in schools, it would encourage the children to be well-immersed in it. The study of Samuel (2024) found that there was no significant difference in the factors responsible for truancy among students in secondary schools in Niger State, based on teachers' gender. Olaniyan (2022) also found that there was so significant difference in the causes of truancy among secondary school students in public secondary schools in Lagos State, based on teachers' gender. This means that both male and female teachers agreed that the above factors were factors responsible for truancy among students

Gideon and Eremie (2023) reported that the study conducted by National Center for School Engagement found that repetition, low school graduation level and poor academic records during studies are effects of truancy. Henry (2017) posited that effects of truancy could be short-term and long-term. The short-term include teen-age pregnancy, substance abuse, maladjustment, school dropout, poor academic performance. Long-term covers marital instability, incarceration, violence, adult criminality and job instability. Sani (2018) affirmed that the short-term effects of truancy on students are low educational success, poor social skills, falling behind in school work, and isolation from school peers, while the long term-term effects encompass lowered income and joblessness.

The study of Mueller and Giacomazzi (2016) found that truancy had high level of correlation with delinquencies. The delinquencies include gang activity, substance abuse, and later involvement in adult criminal activity such as vandalism, auto theft, burglary, thus leading to incarceration. Siziya et al. (2017) found in their study that students who involved in truancy had been found to involve in illicit drug use, alcohol drinking, risky sexual practice, and cigarette smoking.

The findings of the study of Mac Gillivray and Mann-Erickson (2016) revealed that students exhibiting truant behaviour have great contribution to day time criminal activities. Musa (2014) concluded that consequences of truancy include but not limited to problematic behaviour with teachers and parents, possibility of drop-out, missing of classes, poor seriousness to academic activities, poor academic performance, threats to life and national development, and uncertain and non-promising future. Oluremi (2013) opined that truancy inhibits effective learning and results in poor academic performance of students. Truancy contributes in no small measure to grave unpalatable consequences both for students indulging in it and the societies where they reside. Baker and Jansen (2020) affirmed that truant students are likely to have lower academic achievement while Garry (2021) maintained that truancy breeds delinquent and unlawful activities. The findings of the study conducted by Lawrence (2023) revealed that there was no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Kogi State based on teachers' gender. Alani (2020) also found that teachers were not significantly different in their opinions on the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ejigbo Local Government Area, Osun State.

Statement of the Problem

Students are expected to stay in classroom from the beginning of the first period to the last period from Mondays to Fridays, to be able to acquire adequate knowledge which would enhance their academic performance. However, as gathered from some teachers and principals of some schools and members of the public, in recent times during the school hours, some students of public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State are found playing Table Tennis or Football, gambling at the betting centres, begging for money and go home when the schools close as if they attended all the lessons. Not only that, some parents or guardians do instruct their children to come home before the closing time, for the purpose of hawking for them. All these are tantamount to truancy and they could have negative on such students.

Many Researchers have conducted some studies which are related to this study. Oluremi, (2013) investigated truancy and academic performance of secondary school students in Southwestern Nigeria: Implications for counselling. Sa'ad et al (2017) examined the investigation into the causes of truancy among public senior secondary school students in Azare metropolis of Bauchi State, Nigeria. Sani (2018) conducted a study on the impact of truancy on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Malumfashi Education Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. However, none of the scholars mentioned above investigated the causes and effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. Therefore, this formed the academic gap which this study filled.

Objectives of the Study

The study:

- i. determined the teachers' perception on the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State;
- ii. examined the teachers' perception on the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State;
- iii. investigated the difference in the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers' gender; and
- iv. found the difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Research Questions

- i. What are the teachers' perception on the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State?
- ii. What are the teachers' perception on the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Methodology

In conducting this study, descriptive research design of survey type was employed. One thousand three hundred and fifty seven teachers in the 42 public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area formed population of the study. Twenty one schools (50%) were randomly selected. Out of the 868 teachers in the sampled schools, 266 were proportionally selected, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample size determination. Causes and Effects of Truancy on Students Questionnaire (CETSQ) was utilised for data collection. The instrument was segmented into Sections A, B and C. Section 'A' focused on the demographic information of the respondents, 'B' contained 10 items on the Causes of Truancy, while 'C' had 10 items on the Effects of Truancy. Three experts ensured validity of the instrument. Thirty copies of the instruments were administered to some teachers, who were not part of those sampled for the study. The data gathered were subjected to analysis using Cronbach's Alpha. Reliability index of .85 and 0.77 was realised for the Causes and effects of Truancy respectively. The overall reliability index was 0.81. This affirmed that the instrument was reliable for use. Research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, while t-test was used to test the two hypotheses. Mean scores less than 2.50 were considered 'Rejected', while 2.50 and above were adjudged 'accepted.'

Results

Research Question One: What are the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State?

Table 1

Causes of Truancy among Public Secondary School Students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

S/N	Items	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Broken home	266	3.71	1.32	Accepted
2.	Poor interest in learning	266	3.05	.99	Accepted
3.	Peer influence	266	3.32	1.22	Accepted
4.	Poverty	266	3.40	1.16	Accepted
5.	Poor parenting	266	2.99	.85	Accepted
6.	Nonchalant attitude of teachers	266	3.22	1.07	Accepted
7.	Bullying of students	266	3.05	.98	Accepted
8.	Weak school management	266	2.79	.53	Accepted
9.	Societal distractions	266	3.02	.93	Accepted
10.	Family type	266	3.15	.92	Rejected

Mean scores less than 2.50 = Rejected; 2.50 and above = Accepted

As shown in Table 1, items 1 to 10 had mean scores which are not less than 2.50; therefore, all the items are accepted. This depicts that broken home, poor interest in learning, peer influence, poverty, poor parenting, nonchalant attitudes of teachers, bullying of students, weak school management, societal distractions and family type were causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State.

Research Question two: What are effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State?

Table 1

Effects of Truancy on Public Secondary School Students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

S/N	Items	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Poor academic performance	266	3.16	1.29	Accepted
2.	Inadequate learning	266	2.67	.81	Accepted
3.	Involvement in examination malpractice	266	3.21	1.05	Accepted
4.	Blurred future	266	3.31	1.12	Accepted
5.	Joining of cultists	266	2.72	.65	Accepted
6.	Drug abuse	266	3.38	1.16	Accepted
7.	Stealing	266	3.22	1.07	Accepted
8.	Imprisonment	266	2.82	.71	Accepted
9.	Dropout	266	3.49	1.30	Accepted
10.	Loss of respect for the school authorities	266	3.30	.98	Accepted

Mean scores less than 2.50 = Rejected; 2.50 and above = Accepted

From table 2, the mean scores of items 1 to 10 are not less than 2.50; hence, the decision taken on all them was ‘accepted’. This signifies that poor academic performance, inadequate learning, involvement in examination malpractice, blurred future, drug abuse, stealing, imprisonment, dropout, and lack of respect for the school authorities were the effects on truancy on public secondary school students Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.

Results

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers’ gender.

Table 3

Difference in the Causes of Truancy among Public Secondary School Students Based on Teachers’ Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	101	3.01	.83			
				2.49	.074	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	67	3.25	1.17			

Table 3 showed the calculated t-value (2.49), a mean difference of 0.24 and the p-value (0.74) which is greater than 0.05, which stands for the level of significance. As a result of this outcome, null hypothesis one was accepted. This means that there was no significant difference in the causes of truancy among public secondary school students based on teachers’ gender.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on teachers’ gender.

Table 4

Difference in the Effects of Truancy on Public Secondary School Students Based on Teachers’ Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	101	3.10	.80			
				2.41	.069	Ho ₂ Accepted
Female	67	3.24	1.22			

Table 4 showed the calculated t-value (2.41), a mean difference of 0.14 and the p-value (0.69) which is greater than the level of significance (0.05). Based on this result, null hypothesis two was accepted. This connotes that there was no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students based on teachers' gender.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State were broken home, poor interest in learning, peer influence, poverty, poor parenting, nonchalant attitudes of teachers, bullying of students, weak school management, societal distractions and family type. This finding corroborates the finding of Samuel (2024) that poor teaching skills, bullying, poor managerial skills of managers, parental or guardian influence, peer influence, poor economy and societal influence were factors responsible for truancy among students in secondary schools in Niger State. This finding agrees with the findings of Lawrence (2023) that the parents or guardians, teachers, students, government and members of the society were the causes truancy among public secondary school students in Kogi State.

The findings of the study revealed that effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State were poor academic performance, inadequate learning, involvement in examination malpractice, blurred future, drug abuse, stealing, imprisonment, dropout, and loss of respect for the school authorities were the effects on truancy on public secondary school students Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. This finding is in tandem with the findings of Olaniyan (2022) which revealed that consequences of truancy among secondary school students in public secondary schools in Lagos State were spoor academic achievement, partial learning, cheating, stealing, substance abuse, uncertain future, hooliganism and prostitution. This finding agrees with the findings of Alani (2020) that the effects truancy on public secondary school students in Ejigbo Local Government Area, Osun State were substance abuse, repetition, low academic achievement, examination malpractice, drug abuse and stealing.

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of truancy among public secondary school students based on teachers' gender. This finding supports the findings of Olaniyan (2022) also found that there was so significant difference in the causes of truancy among secondary school students in public secondary schools in Lagos State. Based on teachers' gender. The finding is also in tandem with the finding of Samuel (2024) which showed that there no was significant difference in the factors responsible for truancy among students in secondary schools in Niger State, based on teachers' gender.

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students based on teachers' gender. This finding agrees with what Alani (2020) found that teachers were not significantly different in their opinions on the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Ejigbo Local Government Area, Osun State. This finding also supports the findings of Lawrence (2023) that there was no significant difference in the effects of truancy on public secondary school students in Kogi State based on teachers' gender.

Conclusion

The study concluded that broken home, poor interest in learning, peer influence, poverty, poor parenting, nonchalant attitudes of teachers, bullying of students, weak school management, societal distractions and family type were causes of truancy among public secondary school students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State were. Its effects on students included poor academic performance, inadequate learning, involvement in examination malpractice, blurred future, drug abuse, stealing, imprisonment, dropout, and loss of respect for the school authorities. Also, significant difference did not exist in the teachers' perception on the causes and effects on truancy on students based on gender.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. School counsellors should periodically sensitise students on the consequences of truancy, to make them see the reasons they should always be in their respective classrooms during the school hours to acquire knowledge.
- ii. School managements should be more proactive by giving punishment to the truant students, chastise them on the assembly ground and also ask them to bring their parents or guardians to schools for instant notification and correction, to stop them from the bad habit and also serve as deterrent to others.
- iii. Parents and guardians should keep more surveillance on their children by periodically checking them in schools, give their teachers phone calls to confirm whether they stay in schools or not and desist from any act which could encourage children to indulge truancy.
- iv. Teachers should intensify efforts in the discharge of their duties and be friendlier to students, to stimulate them to always want to be in their respective classrooms to acquire knowledge.
- v. In the interest of their future, students should always stay in the classroom to learn and stay away from their colleagues who could infest them with truancy.

References

- Adekunle, E. S. (2015). *Truancy among public secondary school students: Implications for counselling*. Retrieved from <http://rjopes.emergingresource.org/articles/TRUANCY%20AMONG%20PUBLIC.pd>
- Alani, H. O. (2020) Assessing teachers' opinions on the effects and solutions to truancy on public secondary school students in Ejigbo Local Government Area, Osun State. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 3(1), 34-42.
- Baker, D., & Jansen, J. (2020). Using groups to reduce elementary school absenteeism. *Social Work in Education*, 22(1), 46-53.
- Ehinder, S. A. (2015). Truancy among public secondary school students. Implications for counselling. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)* 6(7), 331-338.
- Ezeani, P. T., Ogu, C., & Sabboh, G. M. (2023). Parental involvement as correlate of career decision-making among secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 4(4), 106-115.

- Garry, E. M. (2001). *Truancy: First step to lifetime of problems*. US Department of Justice.
- Gideon, T., & Eremie, M. (2023). Psychological variables as predictors of truancy reduction among students in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Social Science and Management Studies*, 2(4), 14-28. <https://rajournals.net/index.php/ijssms/article/view/171>.
- Henry, K. L. (2017). Who's skipping school: Characteristics of truants in 8th and 10th Grade. *The Journal of School Health*, 77, 29-35.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Management*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Lawrence, J. A. (2023). Causes and effects of truancy among public secondary school students in Kogi State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 2(2), 56-63.
- Mac Gillivray, H., & G. Mann-Erickson. (2016). Data to drive decisions: school attendance, truancy and juvenile crime in Denver. A presentation delivered on April 28, 2016 in Denver. National Center for School Engagement.
- Mueller, D., & Giacomazzi, A. (2006). Dealing with chronic absenteeism and its related consequences: the process of and short-term effects of a diversionary juvenile court intervention. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 11(2), 199-219.
- Musa, T. M. (2014). Absenteeism and truancy on academic performance of secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(22), 81-87.
- Olaniyan, K. E. (2022). Causes and consequences of truancy among secondary school students in public secondary schools in Lagos State. *Journal of Arts Education*, 1(1), 57-64.
- Oluremi, F. D. (2013). Truancy and academic performance of secondary school students in Southwestern Nigeria: Implications for counselling. *International Journal for Cross-Disciplinary Subjects in Education*, 3(2), 1424-1428.
- Sa'ad, T. U., Sabo, S., & Dahuwa, A. A. (2017). Investigation into the causes of truancy among public senior secondary school students in Azare metropolis of Bauchi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(5), 40-45.
- Samuel, G. L. (2024). Assessing the factors responsible for truancy among students in secondary schools in Niger State. *Journal of educational Management*, 2(1), 67-75.
- Sani, I. (2018). *Impact of truancy on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Malumfashi Education Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria*. An M.Ed. Dissertation Submitted to the Department of Education, Bayero University, Kano.
- Siziya, S., Muula, S., & Rudatsikira, E. (2017). Prevalence and correlates of truancy among adolescents in Swaziland: Findings from the Global School-Based Health Survey. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health*, 1, 1-15.
- Van Breda, M. J. (2016). Guidelines for empowering secondary school educators in Loco parents in addressing truancy among early adolescent learners university of South Africa. *Journal of Guidance and counselling*, 2(1), 45-56.